
The Role of Social Media in Influencing Consumer Purchasing Decisions

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Abstract:

In today's time social media play a very important role. In busy time schedule many people want to purchase goods and satisfy their needs through social media. Today's large population connected through social media for satisfying their different needs and requirement. Most of the business organisation also wants to sell the commodity through social media. Today's world is considered as digital world. All people are connected through internet with each other. so social media play a very different role as well as important role on purchasing behaviour of consumer.

Keywords: *Social media, Consumer, Consumer behaviour, Consumer Decision Process, Online sites.*

Introduction:

A study based on the decision making process of consumers behaviour. In recent days each and every people are connected to social media. Social media create a good impact on consumers standard of living. On social media people connected with each other and they are sharing their views, thoughts with each other. Now a days many business organisations selling their goods and services through social media. It is a good platform for upcoming, growing as well as exiting business to sell the commodity through social media as well as earn more and more profit. Social media giving opportunity to upcoming business without investing a large amount of capital to start a business and earn a good amount of profit.

In today's busy schedule people find to purchase the commodity online without wasting time spending in a market. Online

marketing it is a new trend come in commerce and trend.

Many consumers purchasing the commodity online or we can say that social media.

In today's busy time schedule or we can say or hectic time schedule people having very limited time with them. So they are not able to visit every time market and purchase the commodity, so people ready to purchase the commodity through online mode or social media.

Consumer:

A consumer is a individual /person who purchase the commodity for his/her personal purposes. In other words we can say that consumer is a person who consume or purchase the commodity for satisfying its own needs and requirements. He /she purchase the commodity not for sale purpose. In today's time consumer is the

king of the market. All the goods and services produced in accordance with the requirement of the consumers.

Social Media:

Social media is the online platforms where each and every individual person can share information and connect with each other without any difficulties and restrictions. It is group of people connected with each other for sharing views and content with each other. Example of social media is You Tub, Twitter, Facebook, instagram; LinkedIn etc. these sites create more impact on people standards of living. Large number of people connecting through social media therefore today's business organisation finding good platforms for selling a commodity to large group of people on large basis and earns more profits.

Social Media and Marketing:

Social media marketing is the open platforms to these entire small, medium and large organizations for selling their commodities. All small and large size business advertises the products through social media and captures a large number of populations from the society to earn the large amount of profits. Attractive advertisement attracts all population which is connected through social media. Social media guides the business organisation what is needs and requirements of consumers, their like and dislike, fashion, trends going on in a market etc. after collecting all such valuable information business firm change

in their products and sale in the market and earn a good amount of profits.

Objectives of the Study:

1. To study the effects of social media on consumers buying behavior.
2. To understand how business can engage more customers to earn large profit.

Literature Review:

1. Varghese, S., Nandhini M [6] explained its study that demographic factors effects on consumers buying behaviour. Also stated that now days social media paly a very important role on consumers purchasing behaviour.
2. Nima Barhemmati [2] 18. Found in his study social media play a very important role for advertising products. Due to advertising a products business firms earn a large amount of profits without any difficulties. For earning any good image in the market, publicity, goodwill etc. strong advertisements required and this platform provide by social media.
3. Gupta, S., Agarwal, A. K., & Chauhan, A. K [4]. This article state that increasing the craze of social media as compare to past years in recent times business firms earning a large amount of profits without investing a large amount of capital as well saving their times and efforts.
4. Godey, B., Manthiou, A., Pederzoli, D., Rokka, J., Aiello, G., Donvito, R., & Singh, R [3]. This article stated that now a days social media increasing very fast. Large number of business uses a social media for marketing purpose. Many business organisation use the social media for product awareness.

Research Methodology:

Data Collection Method:

Data Collection method used secondary data. For secondary data studied a

different research articles related to same topics.

Scope of the Research:

Taking the objectives of the research into account, conducting the study from the viewpoint of the consumer would be the ideal approach. The researcher conducts this study to help consumers identify reasons regarding how social media changed their buying decisions. The main purpose of marketing is about analysing the needs of the consumer therefore in the consumer decision making process.

Social Media & Consumer Behaviour:

- Information about various brands, promotions, discounts and offers are posted on social media sites, social media and website is a very good way to receive information about everything without great amount of efforts, thereby, majority of people tend to follow various brands on social media.
- Social media is like megaphone to generate information about the brands to the customers, brands can shine and create an advantage through this medium by generating positive information about their products and services of the respondents stated that social media does affect the vision of the brand in the minds of the customers. This can have a negative impact for the brand in a case where there are few bad reviews about the brand on social media, the target audience might consider it to be the trust and not buy the product or service from that brand. Whereas, the minority of people said that social media does not affect the perception of the brand, they believe mostly in trying the product and service and then judging it instead of looking at its promotion on various websites
- All kinds of businesses have turned to social media to find and connect with their target market. Consumer buying decision is affected by the social media

promotions. People agree that social media does influence the purchase, whereas people are neutral in this and a very few people disagree to this fact.

Recommendations

- Companies can be more connected with customers through Social media because the brands can communicate with them regularly and help or guide them to make a better purchase decision. Companies can use Social media more frequently to draw the consumer attention and brand awareness.
- Brands can share more positive experience of the customers who have already used that product so that the prospects and the ones who are already planning to buy can relate themselves more.
- Companies should give more importance to Social media marketing. Their presence on Social media can give them more visibility and it can also increase the brand value that will lead to more customer loyalty and customer lifetime value.

Conclusion:

The data collected through the questionnaire is from the consumer's point of view so that new insights can be determined. The research also aims to help potential readers understand the importance of social media websites/apps The research has shown a powerful impact of Social media on consumer buying behaviour in digital age. No doubt that Social media had brought major changes to both, consumer as well as businesses. The research has shown that consumers are highly selective while making a purchase. Though there is a plenty of data and sources of information on Social media, still personal attitude of the consumers makes a lot of difference in selecting and making a purchase.

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